
D4.2 / The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem (Alpha version)

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List of abbreviations

AAR	Android Archive
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BART	Balloon Analogue Risk Task
BBI	Beat-to-Beat Interval
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
dBM-DEV	Digital Biomarkers Development
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
HCP	Health Care Professional
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PD	Parkinson's Disease
PGO	PostgreSQL Operator
RBD	REM sleep Behaviour Disorder

Executive summary

The goal of Deliverable 4.2, 'The AI-PROGNOSIS Digital Health Ecosystem (Alpha Version),' is to serve as a companion report detailing the development of the AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem applications (mAI-Health, mAI-Care, and mAI-Insights). It highlights the progress from initial user requirements gathering through co-creation workshops to deploying functional alpha-version prototypes.

These applications serve different user groups, including individuals at risk of developing Parkinson's Disease, patients, and healthcare professionals. Built as part of the ecosystem's Minimum Viable Products (MVPs), they incorporate advanced data collection and processing mechanisms, such as smartwatch integration, a custom virtual keyboard, and active digital cognitive function tests.

The development strategy emphasises containerised deployment, continuous integration, and robust system performance. Key components include the Ingest Application Programming Interface (API), which securely aggregates diverse health data, and the artificial intelligence (AI) Models API, which provides predictive insights. Deployment leverages Kubernetes for scalability, Argo CD for GitOps-based configuration management and monitoring stack, including Prometheus and Grafana, for performance measurement. The system prioritises data security and resilience, integrating real-time alerts and automated backups to ensure reliability.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document scope

The D4.2 deliverable is part of WP4, 'The AI-PROGNOSIS Digital Health Ecosystem,' and is the product of tasks T4.2 'Application Design and Development', T4.3 'Data storage and analytics infrastructure', and T4.4 'System orchestration, verification and monitoring'. It serves as a companion report to the alpha versions of the 'mAI' digital health ecosystem MVPs for Parkinson's disease screening and care, i.e., mAI-Health, mAI-Care, and mAI-Insights applications.

It builds upon and expands the containers and many of the components from D4.1, 'Initial Technical Specifications, Architecture, and Product Backlog', where they were initially identified, while also incorporating new components identified during development. This deliverable will also feed the updates of the technical specifications and system architecture in D4.3 'Updated Technical Specifications, Architecture, and Product Backlog', and will serve as a baseline for the applications delivered in D4.4 'The AI-PROGNOSIS Digital Health Ecosystem (MVP)'.

1.2 Document structure

The document includes six sections, and it is structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides a brief introduction to the present document.
- Section 2 describes the preparatory work done to identify the requirements and features that the applications will include.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the applications and the components they include.
- Section 4 gives a detailed description of the components.
- Section 5 describes the system's deployment specifications.
- Section 6 concludes with a summary of the next steps towards the MVPs.

2 Preparatory work

In order to reach the alpha version of the mAI digital health ecosystem's MVPs, extensive planning was required.

Firstly, the main features that the applications included had to be identified. For this particular reason, partner UU, leading user research and co-creation activities, conducted co-creation workshops with a patient panel (see D2.1 'Initial report on user research and cocreation') and relevant health care professionals (HCPs) to identify the user needs for all MVPs; the needs were documented in D2.1 'Initial report on user research and co-creation'. From there, SQD, leading software development, translated all identified user needs into functional requirements, non-functional requirements and user stories and documented them in D4.1 'Initial technical specifications, architecture and product backlog', along with the ecosystem's initial architecture.

A key point that influenced development was the selection of the smartwatch that will be paired with the applications for passively collecting motion and physiological data, required for digital biomarker measurement. After market research, Garmin vívoactive 5¹ was chosen and access to Garmin's Health Software Development Kit (SDK) was obtained. The SDK enables pairing

¹ Garmin vívoactive 5: <https://www.garmin.com/en-US/p/1057989>

and synchronisation between the smartwatch and a smartphone, and collection of low-level sensor data, including, among others, 3-axis accelerometer data, photoplethysmography (PPG)-based beat-to-beat intervals (BBI), and PPG-based heart rate.

During the development of the applications, AI-PROGNOSIS partners contributed their know-how on core application elements. AUTH provided and helped with the integration of a custom virtual keyboard ('Research keyboard'), which collects keystroke-related data². Clinical partners TUD and CHUT assisted with the implementation of three active cognitive tests.

For the needs of the first clinical study of the project, the dBM-DEV study, a predecessor of the mAI-Health application, the dBM-DEV study application version, was developed. This application consolidates core data collection functionalities, including collection of data from the smartwatch, the active cognitive tests, the custom virtual keyboard, and user self-reporting questionnaires (for more details see Section 3.1). These functionalities will be part of one or both of the mAI-Health and mAI-Care MVP versions.

Lastly, since part of the intended use of the mAI-Care application is to help persons with Parkinson's Disease (PD) track their symptoms through digital biomarkers, a co-creation workshop with the patient panel was conducted to gather feedback on some data visualisations.

3 Container level

To comply with the structure of D4.1, the C4 model³ will be utilised in this document as well, using the terms 'containers' for the applications and 'components' for pieces of code that cannot be independently deployed. The containers will be described briefly along with all their included components. **Table 1** summarises each container's userbase.

All mobile application containers are being developed in React Native using Expo⁴, a TypeScript framework that enables building mobile applications with flexibility using a plethora of open-source libraries. Parts of the application that need to interact with other packages, such as Garmin's Health SDK, were developed using native code (specifically Kotlin programming language). At this stage, the applications are only available for Android.

Requirements for full usage of the mobile applications:

- A smartphone device with Android 11 or higher (API level 30)
- Minimum 250MB free storage for installation, with a recommended 3GB available for storage of collected data.
- A Garmin vívoactive 5 smartwatch device.
- Connection to the internet via Wi-Fi.

The mAI-Insights web application, intended for HCPs, is being developed using Next.js⁵ with TypeScript, a React framework that enables developers to build fast, scalable and search engine optimisation (SEO)-friendly web applications by offering features like server-side rendering, static site generation, API routes and automatic code optimisation.

² Keystroke-related data are used for the assessment of slowness of fine movements – see D3.1 'First report on digital biomarkers for PD' for details.

³ The C4 model: <https://c4model.com>

⁴ Expo: <https://docs.expo.dev/>

⁵ Next.js: <https://nextjs.org/>

The only requirements to access the mAI-Insights web application are:

- A device with internet connection (preferably a computer for optimal experience).
- A relatively new version of a modern web browser, such as Chrome, Firefox, or Safari.

Table 1 Userbase of mAI digital health ecosystem applications

Userbase	dBM-DEV study app	mAI-Health	mAI-Care	mAI-Insights
Persons without PD	✓	✓		
Persons with PD	✓		✓	
Healthcare Professionals				✓

3.1 dBM-DEV study application container

For the needs of the dBM-DEV study, the dBM-DEV study version of the mAI-Health application was developed. This version of mAI-Health includes also components that are intended for the mAI-Care MVP (**Table 2**). The application is available in four languages: English, French, German, and Spanish.

Table 2 List of components used in the dBM-DEV study app

Component ID	Component name
COMP-SSM	Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism
COMP-WOR	Data collection worker
COMP-LDB	Local database
COMP-CVK	Research keyboard
COMP-ACT	Active cognition capturing tests
COMP-NCM	Notification channel manager

3.1.1 Installation and first usage

The application can be downloaded from the Google Play Store⁶. Once downloaded and installed, the user needs to log in (see **Figure 1**). Currently, credentials are generated by partner INTRA, responsible for the data management infrastructure, and are available only for dBM-DEV study participants; a test user account is provided in Section 6 for demonstration purposes. After successful authentication, the user proceeds with the onboarding process.

During onboarding, the user is asked to provide personal details, specifically sex at birth, age, height, weight, bedtime and wake-up time (user consents to provide the information during study enrolment). This information is needed for the pairing and configuration of the smartwatch. The wake-up time is saved also in the AI-PROGNOSIS backend and used for setting the time at which the notifications about the user's tasks will be sent.

The next steps of the onboarding (see **Figure 1**) include:

- Enabling notifications preferences,
- Selecting on which wrist the user will wear the smartwatch,
- Opting in for the sleep feedback question,

⁶ mAI-Health (dBM-DEV study version): <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.squaredev.maihealth>

- Pairing the smartwatch with the mobile device,
- Enabling data collection (see Section 4.2),
- Installing the Research keyboard (see Section 4.4) and lastly,
- Inform the user about how they can request help or send feedback and provide access to the privacy policy and terms of use of the app.

Figure 1 dBM-DEV study application log-in and onboarding

3.1.2 Application navigation

The application's bottom navigation bar includes three tabs: the home screen, the 'Practice tests' tab, and the 'Profile' tab.

3.1.2.1 Home screen

On the home screen (see **Figure 2**), the user can view the days they are participating in the study, the last timestamp of the logged data from the smartwatch, and their current and upcoming tasks.

During the first login, the only task visible to users under their current tasks is a sleep feedback question, provided that they have opted in. The sleep feedback question asks the user daily if

they experienced a REM sleep Behaviour Disorder (RBD) incident the previous night and is part of the dBM-DEV study protocol.

A week after the first log-in, the active cognitive tests are listed under the 'Upcoming tasks' with the indication of when the user needs to perform them (see Section 4.5). Once listed under the 'Current tasks', the user has five days to complete them, with the last day of availability clearly indicated. The aforementioned follow the protocol of the dBM-DEV study.

Figure 2 dBM-DEV study application home screen

3.1.2.2 Practice tests

The three active tests are also available in the 'Practice tests' tab, allowing the users to practice them. The data from these practice tests are not saved.

3.1.2.3 Profile

The 'Profile' tab consists of three different subsections: 'Account', 'Settings' and 'Support'. The application version is also viewable.

Account

In Account, the users can view their personal details entered during onboarding, the privacy policy, and terms of use of the application, and can log out.

Settings

In Settings, the user can:

- Unpair the smartwatch,
- Set up the Research keyboard (if not done during onboarding) (see Section 4.4),
- Stop the data collection,
- Enable/Disable the sleep feedback question and,
- Enable/Disable task notifications.

Contact

The user can view the contact information of the clinical site through which they were enrolled.

3.1.3 Notifications

There are five different types of notifications that the user of the application can receive (for more details, see Section 4.8):

1. Sleep feedback question notifications (see **Figure 3**),
2. Active cognitive test notifications,
3. Data collection notifications,
4. Bluetooth connection notifications and,
5. Wi-Fi connection notifications.

Figure 3 Sleep feedback notification

3.2 mAI-Health container

The mAI-Health application is intended for persons without PD to help them track their risk under the supervision of a primary or secondary care HCP. The primary mission is to collect data from the user that will be used by the PD risk prediction model developed by the AI-PROGNOSIS, the output of which will be communicated and monitored by the attending HCP through the mAI-Insights web application. **Table 3** lists the components included in the alpha version of mAI-Health.

Table 3 List of components used in the alpha version of mAI-Health

Component ID	Component name
COMP-SSM	Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism
COMP-WOR	Data collection worker
COMP-LDB	Local database
COMP-CVK	Research keyboard
COMP-SRQ	Self-reporting questionnaires
COMP-NCM	Notification channel manager

3.2.1 Installation and first usage

The application is currently available as an APK for download (see Section 6). The sign-in and onboarding screens are similar to the dBM-DEV study application but with certain differentiations, as this is an evolution of the latter toward the MVP:

- Before signing in, the user can register for an account (this feature is not yet implemented) (see **Figure 4**).
- The user is prompted to connect with their attending doctor. To do so, they must enter a code corresponding to their doctor or scan a provided QR code. A request is then

sent to the doctor that has to accept it via the mAI-Insights web application (this feature is not fully implemented).

- There is no option to enable the sleep feedback question.

3.2.2 Application navigation

The application’s navigation bar includes three tabs: the home screen, the ‘Learn’ tab, and the ‘Profile’ tab.

3.2.2.1 Home screen

On the home screen (see **Figure 5**), the user can view the days they have been monitoring their PD risk, the last timestamp of the logged data from the smartwatch, and their current and upcoming tasks.

Upon first log-in, the user is prompted to complete a lifestyle and medical history profile through a questionnaire listed under the Current Tasks. The task is active until it is completed (see Section 0). Once completed, it will reappear as a Health update task after 6 months. The questionnaire includes questions about known risk and prodromal markers of PD as defined by the Movement Disorders Society (Heinzel et al, 2019) that can be self-reported by the user. As part of the AI-PROGNOSIS PD risk assessment system under development, the information will be combined with a digital risk score derived from smartwatch-collected sleep, mobility, and physiological data to decide on the status of the user against PD.

Figure 4 mAI-Health welcome screen

Figure 5 mAI-Health home screen

Figure 6 'You doctor' tab in mAI-Health

3.2.2.2 Learn

In this section, educational articles on PD will be listed that the users can access (not yet implemented) to learn more about PD diagnosis and how new technologies, such as those of AI-PROGNOSIS, can help.

3.2.2.3 Profile

The profile tab consists of four different sub-sections, 'Account', 'Your doctor', 'Settings', and 'Support'. The application version is also viewable.

Account

In the Account subsection, users can view and edit the personal details they entered during onboarding (for now, these are not saved anywhere other than on the user's device). They can also access the application's privacy policy and terms of use and log out.

Your doctor

In this sub-section, the user has access to the details of their connected doctor (see **Figure 6**). They can also connect to a doctor if they have not done so during the onboarding process or switch to another doctor. The user is also informed that mAI-Health sends risk reports to the connected doctor automatically and that they should contact their doctor to learn more.

Settings

Settings are the same with the dBM-DEV study app, apart from the option to enable/disable the sleep feedback question (see Section 3.1.2.3 and **Figure 7**).

Contact

The Contact sub-section is the same as the dBM-DEV study application (see Section 3.1.2.3 and **Figure 8**).

Figure 7 'Settings' tab in mAI-Health

Figure 8 'Contact' tab in mAI-Health

3.2.3 Notifications

The mAI-Health application currently generates three types of user notifications (see Section 4.8):

1. Data collection notifications (see **Figure 9**),
2. Bluetooth connection notifications and,
3. Wi-Fi connection notifications (see **Figure 10**).

Figure 9 Data collection notification

Figure 10 Bluetooth and Wi-Fi connectivity notifications

3.3 mAI-Care container

The mAI-Care application will be used by individuals diagnosed with PD who want to track their symptoms with the help of their attending secondary care HCP. Unlike mAI-Health, the users will have access to tracked digital biomarkers of certain symptoms. At the same time, certain tracked data will serve as input to the PD progression prediction model that the project develops, the output of which will be communicated, inter alia, to the attending HCP via the mAI-Insights app. **Table 4** lists the components of the alpha version of the mAI-Care app.

Table 4 List of components used in the alpha version of mAI-Care

Component ID	Component name
COMP-SSM	Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism
COMP-WOR	Data collection worker
COMP-LDB	Local database
COMP-CVK	Research keyboard
COMP-ACT	Active cognition capturing tests
COMP-NCM	Notification channel manager
COMP-VIS	Data visualisations

3.3.1 Installation and first usage

The installation, sign-in, and onboarding process are identical to the mAI-Health application (see Section 3.2.1).

3.3.2 Application navigation

The application’s navigation bar consists of four tabs: the home screen and the ‘Practice tests’, ‘Visualisations’ (temporary title), and ‘Profile’ tabs.

3.3.2.1 Home screen

On the home screen (see **Figure 11**), similarly to the dBM-Dev study app, the user can see the days they have been monitoring their condition, the last timestamp of the logged data from the smartwatch, and their current and upcoming tasks.

The tasks are similar to those available in the dBM-DEV study app, with the difference that there is no sleep feedback question (see Section 3.1.2.1).

Figure 11 mAI-Care home screen

Figure 12 mAI-Care visualisations screen

3.3.2.2 Practice tests

This tab is the same as the corresponding one in the dBM-DEV study application (see Section 3.3.2.2).

3.3.2.3 Visualisations

Through this tab, users have access to tracked digital measurements of certain key PD symptoms (see Section 4.7). Digital biomarkers implemented by T3.1 ‘RBD and daytime somnolence tracking’ and T3.2 ‘Motor and cognitive function tracking’ will be the source of measurements. For the time being, the alpha version includes visualisations with mock data (see **Figure 12**).

3.3.2.4 Profile

The profile tab consists of four different subsections: ‘Account’, ‘Your doctor’, ‘Settings’ and ‘Support’, same as mAI-Health (see Section 3.2.2.3).

3.3.3 Notifications

The mAI-Care application currently generates 4 types of user notifications (see Section 4.8):

1. Active cognitive test notifications,
2. Data collection notifications,
3. Bluetooth connection notifications and,
4. Wi-Fi connection notifications.

3.4 mAI-Insights container

The mAI-Insights web application allows HCPs to view data related to users of mAI-Health and mAI-Care applications under their responsibility (**Figure 13** and **Figure 14**), for PD screening and patient follow-up. It will also allow access to the AI-assisted medication decision support (AIMED) module (not implemented yet) powered by the medication response

predictive model AI-PROGNOSIS is developing. Ultimately, HCPs will be able to insert clinical data of patients they are attending, that will also serve as input for the predictive models the project is developing (see Section 2.3.8 of D4.1).

This application is still in a preliminary stage, since, during the first phase of the project, the focus was placed on developing a robust version of the dBM-DEV study app, with optimal user experience and data collection that meets the requirements of the study and the research and development activities of tasks T3.1 and T3.2.

Figure 13 mAI-Insights home screen

Figure 14 mAI-Insights connection requests page

4 Component level

Most of the components identified during the technical specification of the ecosystem have been implemented, either fully or partially. **Table 5** lists the components that have been implemented in at least one of the MVPs.

Table 5 List of components used in the alpha version of the mAI digital health ecosystem applications

Component ID	Component name	dBm-DEV study app	mAI-Health	mAI-Care
COMP-SSM	Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism	✓	✓	✓
COMP-WOR	Data collection worker	✓	✓	✓
COMP-LDB	Local database	✓	✓	✓
COMP-CVK	Research keyboard	✓	✓	✓
COMP-ACT	Active cognition capturing tests	✓		✓
COMP-SRQ	Self-reporting questionnaires		✓	
COMP-NCM	Notification channel manager	✓	✓	✓
COMP-VIS	Data visualisations			✓

4.1 Smartwatch synchronisation mechanism (COMP-SSM)

The smartwatch synchronisation mechanism is a component that facilitates the pairing of the smartwatch with the smartphone, as well as the collection of the raw data from the smartwatch to the application. The collected raw data include 3-axis accelerometer data, BBI and heart rate. Much of the functionality is implemented natively, but some functions are exposed to the React Native side to allow user interaction, such as pairing with the smartwatch.

Through Garmin's Health SDK, which is packaged in an Android Archive (AAR) library, the user pairs Garmin vivoactive 5 smartwatch with his/her smartphone. In order for the SDK to start providing the desired raw data, the logging of data needs to be enabled on the smartwatch. Once this is done, the SDK syncs with the smartwatch, and the data are ready to be retrieved by the data collection worker (see Section 4.2).

4.2 Data collection worker (COMP-WOR)

The data collection worker is a component that collects data from the smartwatch, saves them in the local database and then sends them to the AI-PROGNOSIS databases. It is implemented completely on the native side of the application, since it heavily interacts with Garmin's Health SDK.

In order for the worker to start, the user has to explicitly activate it. Once activated, it runs approximately every 30 minutes, depending on the battery level of the device and the operating system's resource management. No other action is needed from the user, since the component runs in the background. The user is notified though every time the operation begins via a silent push notification.

Upon start, the worker fetches accelerometer, BBI and heart rate data from the smartwatch. During its first run, the collection retrieves data from the past two days, gathering any data recorded during this period. The last timestamp of the received data is saved, and for subsequent runs, this saved timestamp serves as the starting point to minimize collection time

and avoid data duplication. If the last timestamp is more than two days old, it is replaced with the timestamp corresponding to exactly two days ago. This is because the smartwatch cannot store unlimited data and deletes older records in its memory.

Once the data fetching is complete, the data are saved in their corresponding tables in the local SQLite database, and the worker's second task begins: dispatching the data to the backend. The worker queries the database tables and sends the resulting data to the backend via an API call. This call is secure, as a unique access token is requested at the beginning, and the user is authenticated before proceeding. When the backend responds with a status code of 200, indicating that the data were successfully saved in the AI-PROGNOSIS databases, the worker deletes the sent data and continues with the remaining data in the table. If the table is empty, it moves to the next one, repeating this process until all tables are empty. After completing its tasks, the worker is triggered again in about 30 minutes.

A prerequisite for the worker to fetch data from the smartwatch is that the SDK has established a Bluetooth connection with the smartwatch. To send the data to the system's database, a Wi-Fi connection is required.

In the event of an error during data transmission, the data are not deleted but will be retried during the next worker run. If the error is related to authentication, the worker will attempt to refresh the access token. If successful, the process will continue; if it fails, the entire dispatching process will be aborted. For other types of errors, the worker will proceed by sending the next batch of data.

The data collection worker can be stopped by unpairing the smartwatch, disabling it through the app's settings, or logging out of the app.

4.3 Local database (COMP-LDB)

All data collected from the smartwatch, active cognitive tests and self-reporting questionnaires, as well as application monitoring and error logs, are saved in a local SQLite database. For the application to use the least device storage possible, the data are stored only until they are sent to the AI-PROGNOSIS databases; once they have been successfully dispatched, they are deleted from the local storage.

The database is fully implemented on the native side of the app, since most data transactions happen while the data collection worker is running.

4.4 Research keyboard (COMP-CVK)

The Research keyboard (referred to as the custom virtual keyboard in deliverable D4.1) is a custom input method for smartphones running Android developed by AUTH and comes packaged as an AAR library. It passively captures typing-related data, including key tap events and typing settings, in the background during routine typing. Every time a typing session is completed (defined from the time the keyboard appears in the foreground to the time it disappears again), the data are saved in a dedicated SQLite database from where the data collection worker retrieves them.

4.5 Active cognition capturing (cognitive) tests (COMP-ACT)

A set of three tests have been implemented and users are required to perform them every two weeks (per the dBM-DEV study protocol). The tests serve to assess aspects of the user's cognitive function.

- **A memory test:** The N-back memory test assesses the memory skills of the user. The user is presented with a stimulus and is then asked to remember if it matches the stimulus from the previous step (see **Figure 15**). There are 50 rounds and, in each round, the reaction time of the users, as well as whether the choice of the stimulus was correct are logged.
- **A balloon test:** The Balloon Analogue Risk Task (BART) is a computerised decision-making task that is used to assess risk-taking behaviour. In each round, the user is presented with a balloon that has a random maximum pump limit between 2 and 50. Each pump represents one point and the user has to decide whether they want to keep pumping it to earn more points, with the risk of popping it, or to safely collect the earned points (see **Figure 16**). There are 20 rounds and, in each round, the maximum points of the balloon, the points collected and whether the balloon was popped are logged.
- **A reaction test:** The stop-signal task measures attention by challenging the user to press a specific button based on the direction of an arrow or abstain from doing so if a red cross appears. The delay that the red cross appears is adaptive to the reaction time of the user (see **Figure 17**). There are 200 rounds, split in four blocks of 50 rounds each, and in each round, the reaction time, whether the choice was correct, as well as the presence of the red cross and its delay time are logged.

This component is developed completely in React Native and the results at the end of each test are saved in the in-app SQLite database. No internet connection is required during the tests. Data are sent to the AI-PROGNOSIS databases, during the execution of the data collection worker.

Figure 15 Memory test

Figure 16 Balloon test

Figure 17 Reaction test

4.6 Self-reporting questionnaires (COMP-SRQ)

mAI-Health also includes a self-reporting questionnaire. Users answer a set of questions both upon first use of the application and at predefined intervals. The initial questionnaire requires the users to answer questions concerning their lifestyle, family medical history and symptoms that could be associated with PD (see **Figure 18**). The users are then asked to provide an update every six months. mAI-Care will also include a self-reporting questionnaire which is not yet defined.

Figure 18 Self-reporting questionnaire in mAI-Health

4.7 Data visualisations (COMP-VIS)

A preliminary version of the data visualisations has been developed through which the users can see graphs of digital biomarker data to be produced by the data processing pipelines container (for more details, please see Section 2.3.8 of D4.1). The users can choose the time resolution of the graphs (day, week, month and year), depending on the data's nature. Digital

biomarker visualisations - which have been implemented with mock data for the time being, since the online data processing pipelines have not been deployed yet – include measurements of:

- Slowness of movement,
- Dyskinesia,
- Human activity (physical activity) and,
- Rest tremor.

4.8 Notification channel manager (COMP-NCM)

The notification channel manager is implemented as two sub-components, a sub-component in the React Native side where Expo notifications⁷ handles the notifications that are sent from the mAI backend (by automatically configuring and utilizing Firebase Cloud Messaging⁸), and a sub-component on the native side to send local notifications related to the operation of the data collection worker.

There are five different types of notifications a user can receive in mAI-Health and mAI-Care:

React Native side

1. Self-reporting questionnaire notifications (only mAI-Health),
2. Active cognition capturing tests notifications (only mAI-Care),

Native side

3. Data collection notifications,
4. Bluetooth connection notifications (to turn on Bluetooth when it is deactivated) and,
5. Wi-Fi connection notifications (to connect to Wi-Fi to upload data in case of no recent wi-fi connection).

If the user has enabled receiving task reminders, they will be notified when tasks are available to be performed (see **Figure 19**).

Figure 19 Cognitive tests reminder

The data collection worker notification will appear whether the user has reminders enabled or not. This is because the worker uses a foreground service for which the Android operating system demands apps to show a notification each time they run⁹.

The Bluetooth notification will appear once daily when the data collection worker starts and detects no Bluetooth connection. The same applies to the Wi-Fi connection. These notifications cannot be turned off.

⁷ Expo notification: <https://docs.expo.dev/push-notifications/sending-notifications/>

⁸ Firebase Cloud Messaging: <https://firebase.google.com/docs/cloud-messaging>

⁹ Android foreground service: <https://developer.android.com/develop/background-work/services/foreground-services?authuser=2>

5 Deployment specifications

5.1 System overview and data flow

The system architecture supports the sophisticated, data-driven ecosystem for managing and monitoring PD that AI-PROGNOSIS aims to create, with special applications for individuals at risk of PD, PD patients, and HCPs. Integrating several core components and workflows from the architecture enables secure data collection, model-driven insight delivery and personalised health management. Interconnected, the three applications mAI-Health, mAI-Care and mAI-Insights provide a seamless flow of information between user groups while upholding high standards of security and data integrity.

The architecture consists of components, which add up to a seamless, automated environment that enables a user's health journey through data driven insights and clinical support.

Figure 20 System deployment diagram

User authentication and role-based access control is managed by Keycloak¹⁰, an open-source identity and access management solution. Keycloak offers a centralised authentication service that enables the system to assign proper permissions to each user based on the user's role and the service being used; Keycloak is authorising with different permissions an individual using mAI-Health to track personal risk factors, a patient using mAI-Care to monitor disease progression or an HCP using mAI-Insights to screen and adjust treatment. By using this centralised authentication, the system also enforces consistent security policies for each user to access only the data and features that are relevant to their role.

¹⁰ Keycloak: <https://www.keycloak.org/>

The Ingest API (formerly named Data Transfer Controller in D4.1), the core of which is based on FastAPI¹¹, collects data and pushes it into the central database for structured storage. All these data types, such as data from the users' wearable, self-reported information and clinical data from HCPs are transmitted through the Ingest API. The data gateway for the system is this API, which standardises and stores the data in the database in a secure fashion for future processing. The Ingest API also provides a single point for validation of all incoming data to confirm that the incoming data matches the expected format and quality before being stored.

The database cluster serves as the primary storage for all the structured data, from digital biomarkers to self-reported data. The system uses MinIO¹², an object storage solution able to handle large volume of unstructured data efficiently, for larger, unstructured datasets that might be produced from the data processing pipelines or that might require object storage.

The system supports a broad range of Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven analysis over various structured and unstructured data, ensuring data integrity and availability. The system will be powered by the MLFlow¹³ with its AI Models API. This will facilitate the execution of the machine learning models to generate insights and predictions across the system. Within the services, different AI models will be able to be used according to the requirements of each application.

Additionally, in this architecture, Celery¹⁴ was added as a background worker for scheduling and notification management. Celery schedules users' tasks, as well as notification events about them, and sends timely notifications, thus reminding users to input required data and keep them engaged with the apps.

5.2 Deployment strategy

The architecture of the deployment is designed to ensure a reliable, scalable and efficient rollout of the system's constituent parts across the environment. To streamline update, resources management and system stability, the deployment process leverages containerization, container orchestration, GitOps principles and Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) practices.

Many core components of the codebase are containerized with Docker. With this containerization, each service can run in its isolated environment and with all required dependencies preconfigured. After the code is turned into Docker images, they're stored in a container registry, Harbor¹⁵. The registry serves as a repository that manages and can be utilised to deploy different versions of the services conveniently. Upgrades or downgrades - in case of a deployment failure - can be easily applied in addition to portability. Matching the service's docker image version with the appropriate Git tags in the source code repository allows direct investigation and debugging for the service developer. Kubernetes¹⁶ is used to manage and orchestrate the containerized services from the deployment process. With Kubernetes, containerised applications can be run on a scalable and flexible environment that knows how to handle load balancing, auto-scaling and failover.

¹¹ FastAPI: <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>

¹² MinIO: <https://min.io/>

¹³ MLFlow: <https://mlflow.org/>

¹⁴ Celery: <https://docs.celeryq.dev/en/stable/>

¹⁵ Harbor: <https://goharbor.io/>

¹⁶ Kubernetes: <https://kubernetes.io/>

Almost every service, including mAI backend, the Ingest API and the AI Models API, is deployed as a Kubernetes pod. Deployment configurations defined in Kubernetes manifest can describe efficient resource allocation for optimal performance. Kubernetes also manages horizontal scaling, meaning the system can be scaled automatically without losing incoming traffic. The system scales dynamically to possible demands without manual intervention to maintain performance.

Name	Namespace	Container	CPU	Memory	Restarts	Controlled By	Node	QoS
maibackend-scheduler-6d66f9bc98-vxmff	applications		N/A	N/A	1	ReplicaSet	k8s-worke	Best
ai prognosis-maibackend-test-6cc99ccbff-28dn	applications		N/A	N/A	0	ReplicaSet	k8s-worke	Best
ai prognosis-maibackend-7d6f488bc4-6dwq4	applications		N/A	N/A	0	ReplicaSet	k8s-worke	Best
ai prognosis-maibackend-7d6f488bc4-684kf	applications		N/A	N/A	0	ReplicaSet	k8s-worke	Best

Figure 21 Kubernetes pods of the AI-PROGNOSIS applications

The deployment follows GitOps principles by deploying and monitoring the Kubernetes resources via a GitOps tool, Argo CD¹⁷. With GitOps the deployment state is defined declaratively in a Git repository, which is the single source of truth for all configurations. Argo CD detects changes in the codebase or configuration files available in the Git repository and can synchronise the live Kubernetes environment with the repository and push the changes to the latest updates deployed across all the clusters.

With the GitOps approach, the system has version control, a rollback capability, and simple infrastructure management. Any change made to the configuration, such as changes to the number of deployment instances (replicas) and resource allocations, are committed to Git, which keeps them in a clear history and makes them possible to revert quickly if a problem occurs. As a result, updates are rolled out in this continuous deployment process without much disturbance to end users.

With this setup, the functionality is validated, load tests are conducted, and the security of the newly developed services is ensured without impacting the production services.

5.3 Data backup

Given the sensitive nature of health data, ensuring robust data backup and recovery mechanisms is critical to maintaining data integrity and availability. Our system employs multiple layers of backup strategies to safeguard against data loss. Firstly, the PostgreSQL database cluster is configured for high availability, deployed across two Kubernetes worker nodes. This architecture inherently maintains two synchronized copies of the data, providing redundancy at the infrastructure level. Furthermore, the pgBackRest¹⁸ configuration within Crunchy Data's PostgreSQL Operator¹⁹ (PGO) automates scheduled backups. Full backups are taken every three days at 1:00 AM, with daily differential backups executed at 4:00 AM. These backups are securely stored in a MinIO bucket hosted on a separate Kubernetes worker node, adding another layer of isolation and safety.

¹⁷ Argo CD: <https://argo-cd.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

¹⁸ pgBackRest: <https://pgbackrest.org/>

¹⁹ Crunchy Data's PostgreSQL Operator: <https://access.crunchydata.com/documentation/postgres-operator/latest/tutorials/backups-disaster-recovery/backups>

Figure 22 Full and differential cron jobs in PGO cluster

To enhance resilience, all data—comprising the primary database, replica database and MinIO backups—are also stored on Hetzner’s Storage Boxes²⁰, which are attached to the worker nodes. Each of the three storage boxes undergoes daily snapshots at 3:00 AM, 4:00 AM, and 5:00 AM, respectively, ensuring continuous data capture. The system retains the latest 21 snapshots for each machine, offering a three-week recovery window for historical data. Beyond database-specific backups, daily full-disk backups are configured for all infrastructure machines. Each server maintains seven backup slots; when all slots are filled, the oldest backup is automatically removed to make space for the newest one, ensuring continuous availability of recent system states.

Figure 23 Storage box snapshots

This comprehensive backup strategy—spanning high availability, automated database backups, multi-location storage, and infrastructure-level disk backups—provides a robust

²⁰ Hetzner's Storage Boxes: <https://www.hetzner.com/storage/storage-box/>

safety net for healthcare data. These measures not only mitigate the risk of data loss but also ensure swift recovery in case of failures.

5.4 System performance

The observability stack deployed in our system enables comprehensive performance monitoring and troubleshooting by integrating robust tools for metrics, logging, alerting, and visualisation. At its core, Prometheus²¹ is used for collecting metrics from various components, including the infrastructure and the services running within it. These metrics are leveraged by Alertmanager²², which allows the creation of detailed alerting rules to ensure that potential issues are flagged promptly. Alerts are seamlessly integrated with Microsoft Teams (the project management platform AI-PROGNOSIS uses) through a Prometheus-MS Teams connector²³, enabling the operations team to receive real-time notifications when thresholds are breached, improving monitoring and response time.

For visualisation, Grafana²⁴ serves as the central dashboard, consolidating metrics and logs for actionable insights. It displays infrastructure metrics, such as Kubernetes cluster health and PostgreSQL performance data sourced from Crunchy Data's PGO Prometheus exporter²⁵. Additionally, service-specific dashboards provide a detailed view of application-level metrics, including those from the mobile apps deployed in the environment. This ensures both system-wide and granular visibility into the system's performance.

The logging component is powered by Loki²⁶ and Promtail²⁷, enabling centralised log aggregation and querying within Grafana. Application logs are accessible alongside metrics on the same interface, facilitating faster root-cause analysis during incidents. This combination of metrics, alerts, dashboards, and logs ensures that the observability stack provides a holistic view of the system's health, making it easier to maintain optimal performance and proactively address issues across the infrastructure and deployed services.

Figure 24 Grafana dashboards

²¹ Prometheus: <https://prometheus.io/>

²² Alertmanager: <https://prometheus.io/docs/alerting/latest/alertmanager/>

²³ Prometheus-MS Teams connector: <https://github.com/prometheus-msteams/prometheus-msteams>

²⁴ Grafana: <https://grafana.com/>

²⁵ Crunchy Data's PGO Prometheus exporter: <https://access.crunchydata.com/documentation/postgres-operator/latest/guides/exporter-configuration>

²⁶ Loki: <https://grafana.com/oss/loki/>

²⁷ Promtail: <https://grafana.com/docs/loki/latest/send-data/promtail/>

6 Accessing the applications

The mobile applications can be accessed by downloading and installing the APK files:

- APK for [mAI-Health \(dBM-DEV study version\)](#); alternatively through the [Google Play Store](#) (available in Germany, France, Spain, the United Kingdom, Greece, and Belgium)
- APK for [mAI-Health \(alpha version of MVP\)](#),
- APK for [mAI-Care \(alpha version of MVP\)](#).

Notes:

- **Only one** of the above applications can be installed on a single Android device at a time.
- in order to install the applications that come as an APK file, the 'Install unknown apps' option for the application the file is being downloaded with must be enabled.

The mAI-Insights web application can be accessed using a browser:

<https://mai-insights.aiprognosis.squaredev.io/>

A test user was created that can be used to access all above applications. In the next versions, each user will be able to log in only in their corresponding application.

Username: review-user-1

Password: V4nXmYBQr2

7 Conclusions - roadmap to the Minimum Viable Products (MVPs)

The development of the mAI ecosystem applications is on track. The core data collection layer has been implemented. The focus will be now placed on the comprehensive fulfilment of the identified functional requirements, with continuous consideration for potential updates. To achieve this, additional co-creation sessions will be conducted in the first six months of 2025 to validate implemented functionalities and anticipate emerging needs.

Starting the first month in the six-month time plan, co-creation sessions will be held with HCPs and R&D partners responsible for developing data processing pipelines (WP3 'Predicting PD risk, progression and medication response'). These sessions will ensure that mAI-Insights is tailored to meet their specific needs and aligned with the ongoing development. Subsequently, co-creation sessions involving the patient panel will validate visualisations implemented for the mAI-Care application, while also reaffirming user needs already addressed in both mAI-Health and mAI-Care apps. Hands-on testing of the apps and feedback by both the patient panel and HCPs will be the final step in the co-creation phase that will lead to the MVPs.

A high priority in the time plan is also the body tracking-based comprehensive motor function assessment test (see D3.1 'First report on digital biomarkers for PD'). The test's mission is to assess posture, balance, gait and leg agility through a series of physical tasks performed by participants in front of the smartphone camera. The test uses the MediaPipe²⁸ body

²⁸ MediaPipe: <https://developers.google.com/mediapipe>

landmarker, Google's open-source framework for body tracking, to analyse the video stream directly on the device and extract key joint landmarks. Once fully developed and validated, the test will be integrated into the mAI ecosystem, and specifically the dBM-DEV study application and the mAI-Care MVP.

In terms of back-end development, the focus will be placed on deploying the online data processing pipelines and accommodating the additional storage needs. The finalisation of those pipelines by WP3 will further drive the development of the mAI-Care app and mAI-Insights platform. Pipelines will be deployed within the Kubernetes cluster and store the output data appropriately for future use by the mAI-Care and mAI-Insights apps. In the latter case, these data will form the basis of tailored patient reports for HCPs.

References

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